

THE MAIN METHODS OF WRITING COMPLAINT LETTER

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ABSTRACT

The current article is devoted to exploration of letter writing, its types, its definition and the very idea in the field of science and law. The article talks about goals, objectives and tasks of letter writing. Letters are short reports of original research focused on an outstanding finding whose importance means that it will be of interest to scientists in other fields.

A complaint letter is a formal complaint about any unsatisfactory product, service or situation. Complaint letters are also called claim letters, adjustment letters, complaint and adjustment letters, complaint and claim letters.

A complaint letter is written by a customer to an individual or organization in response to a problem or complaint that has arisen. The purpose of the letter is to state the grievance, request action to be taken to resolve the situation and keep records of the complaint about future reference.

A complaint letter is a formal way of bringing attention to a problem or issue that you have with a product, service, company, or individual. It is important to write a complaint letter in a professional and polite manner, as this will help ensure that your issue is taken seriously.

There are three types of complaint letters: formal, informal and email.

- A formal complaint letter is the most common type of complaint letter. It follows a specific format and includes certain elements, such as the date, your contact information, the recipient's contact information and a description of the issue.
- An informal complaint letter is less formal than a complaint letter but still gives the writer an opportunity to express his or her complaint. It can be in any format, written on notebook paper and hand-delivered or sent via email. Informal complaint letters are most often used for personal complaints (for example, if you have a problem with your neighbor's dog).
- An email complaint letter is used when the complaint originates from an online purchase. The complaint may be about a product that was ordered and received, but items were missing or damaged at delivery. This type of complaint also can be used if you have experienced problems with a digital download (for example, music downloads).

The purpose of a formal complaint letter is to:

- a) outline the issue or problem you are having
- b) provide evidence to support your complaint
- c) ask for a resolution to the issue

Before writing a formal complaint letter, be sure to do the following:

- research the company or organization you are complaint against
- gather all of the relevant information related to your complaint
- outline the issue or problem in detail

The format of your complaint letter can help the right person correctly receive it. A complaint letter should start by including the following components:

- the date of the letter
- your name, address, and contact information
- the recipient's name, company name (if applicable), address, and contact information
- a professional salutation, using the recipient's name or their title (such as "Dear manager")
- a clear subject line (if sent as an email)

After writing these components, your first paragraph should define the problem, including descriptive information such as location and the date of occurrence. The following paragraph should briefly explain how the problem can be rectified. In some situations, you may be satisfied with an apology or assurance that the problem will not reoccur. In other cases, you want a product to be repaired or replaced or a full refund.

If you have attached or included any receipts, photos, or documents with your letter, you should mention them here. The final paragraph should suggest a timetable for the action you wish to be taken.

Then close the letter with an appropriate salutation (such as "Sincerely" or "Regards" and your written name and signature. The entire letter should have a reasonable and polite tone. Avoid making any threats with this letter. Finally, keep copies of your complaint letter and all related documents for your own records.

Complaint letters are written to the concerned authorities when you are not satisfied with some service, or you have a problem that needs to be addressed. See to it that you write the letter in a polite manner. The format of a complaint letter follows the format of a [formal letter](#). To write a complaint letter, you can start with the sender's address followed by the date, the receiver's address, the subject, body of the letter, complimentary closing, signature and name in block letters.

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